

Meloidogyne oryzae, a pest of irrigated rice in Surinam

H. A. Segeren-v.d. Oever and M. L. Sanchit-Bekker, Agricultural Experiment Station, Nematology Department, P. O. Box 160, Surinam, South America

We studied rice root-knot nematode *M. oryzae* populations in Nickerie, the main rice cultivating area of Surinam. Rice cultivation on heavy clay soils in the coastal plain is completely mechanized. Root-knot nematode infestation was mainly on higher land within flooded fields. Thorough flooding reduced infestation and plants recovered slightly. Heavily infested rice plants were stunted, with galled roots and yellow-brown leaves. In nematode-infested fields, crop growth often was limited by P deficiency, weed competition, or acid soil.

Adult females and egg masses were embedded in the roots. *M. oryzae* life cycle took about 4 wk at a mean 27°C. Infestation was concentrated in areas where rice had been planted for at least 30 yr — the last 10 with 2 crops annually.

Greenhouse trials determined if *M. oryzae* reduced growth and yield of rice. Three plants per pot were sown in a 10- × 30-cm polyvinyl chloride containers filled with heavy clay soil (pH = 5.5). Ten thousand *M. oryzae* eggs were added to 30 pots and 30 were left uninoculated. Fifteen pots of each group were flooded to ≤ 5 cm and 15 pots were kept without standing water. Although no differences in plant growth were apparent at 45 d after sowing, rice yield was 15% lower in flooded inoculated soil and 9% less in inoculated soil without standing water than in nematode-free pots. Yield was negatively correlated with the number of

galls, eggs, and second-stage larvae in the roots ($r = -0.74$; $r = -0.59$ $p < 0.01$) in the flooded pots.

Five rice varieties (Diwani, Camponi, Pisari, SKK, and Holland) were good *M. oryzae* hosts, as were weeds *Fimbristylis miliacea*, *Echinochloa crus-galli*, *E. colonum*, *Hymenachne amplexicaulis*, and *Eleocharis* sp. The nematode also reproduced on wheat, potato, tomato, sorghum, and plantain, but not on maize, cotton, peanut, sweet pepper, sweet potato, watermelon, or tobacco.

Deep flooding seems to control *M. oryzae* in irrigated rice fields. Because irrigation water is not always available, we tested different seed treatments for nematode control.

In greenhouse trials, carbofuran at 2.4, 4.8, and 7.2 g ai/kg seed reduced galls by 57, 79, and 80%. Oxamyl was ineffective. □

Irrigation Water Management

Water harvesting for rainfed rice cultivation

J. S. Urkurkar, A. S. R. A. S. Sastri, and B. R. Chandrawanshi, Zonal Agricultural Research Station, Jawaharlal Nehru Agricultural University, Raipur, India

Eight percent of 4.7 million ha of rice in central India is rainfed. Drought is a major cause of unstable yields. We developed a water harvesting technique to stabilize yields.

A series of 8 high and low beds (560 m² each) were constructed. Soybean was grown on raised beds and rice in the sunken beds. We estimated the percentage of runoff from high to low beds based on rainfall intensity, infiltration rate, and water balance computations with effective rainfall and Penman's potential evapotranspiration (see table).

About 46% of total rainfall can be harvested as induced runoff. Soybean, which has low water requirement, grows well on the raised beds which feed water onto lower beds where rice is planted. Using this system over 3 yr, soybean and rice yielded an average 2.3 and 2.6 t/ha versus no-treatment fields with 1.5 t/ha. □

Runoff and grain yield using water harvesting.

Year	Seasonal rainfall (mm)	Runoff ^a (mm)	Total water available (mm)		Yield (t/ha)	
			Soybean	Rice	Soybean	Rice
1981	1119	512.7	607	1632	2.2	2.8
1982	792	375.9	416	1168	2.2	2.2
1983	1263	568.4	695	1831	2.4	3.0

^a Runoff was estimated by analyzing intensity of rainfall and infiltration rate as well as through water balance technique.

Soil and Crop Management

Summer storage of azolla in mud pots

S. Venkataramanan and S. Kannaiyan, Agricultural Microbiology Department, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, Tamil Nadu, India

Maintaining azolla populations at high summer temperatures is a major constraint in azolla cultivation. In Apr 1983 we evaluated 2-, 3-, 5-, 8-, or 10-litre mud pots filled with 1, 2, 4, 6, or 8 litres of water or soil extract for azolla

Mud pot for growing azolla during summer, Tamil Nadu, India

Azolla growth in mud pots in summer, Tamil Nadu, India.

Pot capacity (litre)	Pot surface area (cm ²)	Mean azolla growth in water (g)	Mean azolla growth in soil extract (g)
2	176.8	21	23
3	314.3	23	25
5	452.6	25	26
8	616.0	14	19
10	804.5	13	14
CD		1.867	2.146

storage (see figure). The mud pots were made of fine alluvial soil and fired for 3 to 4 d. Similar pots are used to store and cool water in the local villages.

The soil extract was prepared by mixing 1 kg of clay soil with 1 litre of water and then filtering through muslin, Five ppm superphosphate was added to water and 10 ppm to soil with 20 ppm of carbofuran and carbendazim. Each pot

was inoculated with 20 g fresh azolla fronds, and kept in sunlight. Temperature was 35 to 39 °C. The biomass was recorded 10 d after inoculation. The 3- and 5-litre pots encouraged azolla growth (see table). Black rot developed in 8- and 10-litre pots because of the cooling effect. Pots with soil extract solutions were best for azolla maintenance at high temperatures. □

Yield response of rice to phosphorus

A. U. Bhatti and J. K. Khattak, Northwest Frontier Province (NWFD), Agricultural University, Peshawar; and A. H. Gurmani, Agricultural Research Station, Dera Ismail Khan, Pakistan

We studied yield response of rice to P application at the Government Seed Farm, Rakh Mangan, in Dera Ismail Khan. Soil was a clay with 15% CaCO₃, pH 7.7, 0.8% organic matter, 5 ppm Olsen P, 150 ppm available K, and 0.04% N. Pretreatments were 0, 10, 20, or 30 ppm of fertilizer P to ensure that soils varied in initial available P content.

P treatments were in a randomized complete block design with 3 replications in 5- × 2-m plots. P was thoroughly mixed into the surface soil with basal doses of N and K. Plant height, panicles/m², and grain and straw yield were recorded and a combined analysis of the data was done by keeping soil types in main plots and P treatments in subplots.

Rice yielded significantly highest (7.4 t/ha) with 34 kg P/ha + NK (see table). Soil and treatment interactions also were significant. Straw yield and plant height were not significantly affected by P. Effect on number of panicles/m² was significant, and highest at 85 kg P/ha. The response to P treatment at initial soil P level was somewhat linear. As the initial soil P level increased, response to P treatment beyond 34 kg P/ha decreased (see figure). □

Response curves of P for rice at different initial soil P levels, Dera Ismail Khan, Pakistan.

Yield response of rice to P, Dera Ismail Khan, Pakistan.

Treatment (kg/ha)			Grain yield (t/ha) at P content of				Mean yield (t/ha)	Mean straw yield (t/ha)	Mean panicles/m ²	Mean plant height (cm)
N	P	K	5 ppm	15 ppm	25 ppm	35 ppm				
0	0	0	4.4	4.1	4.8	3.3	5.1 d	7.7 b	248 c	100
100	0	75	5.5	5.1	5.5	5.5	5.4 c	12.4 a	325 ab	111
100	17	75	5.9	6.5	6.5	6.7	6.4 b	13.1 a	305 b	109
100	34	75	7.1	7.7	7.7	7.0	7.4 a	12.8 a	320 ab	111
100	51	75	7.1	6.1	6.8	6.7	6.7 b	12.9 a	320 ab	114
100	68	75	7.1	5.8	6.5	6.7	6.5 b	13.4 a	301 ab	115
100	85	75	7.7	5.5	6.4	6.7	6.6 b	13.7 a	331 a	112
Mean			6.40 a	5.82 b	6.31 ab	6.08 b				
Fertilizer					Significant			Significant	Significant	ns
Interactions (fertilizer × soils)					Significant			ns	Significant	ns
Soils					Significant			ns	ns	ns

Means followed by similar letters do not differ significantly from one another.

Management of aged seedlings of medium-duration rices

P. Balasubramaniyan, assistant professor, Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute, Aduthurai 612101, India

We studied the response of 50-d-old IR20 seedlings in a factorial randomized block

Management of 50-d-old IR20 seedlings, Aduthurai, India, 1983-84 thaladi.

Basal N (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)		
	10 × 10 cm	15 × 10 cm	20 × 10 cm
50	3.0	2.8	2.9
62.5	3.1	3.0	3.1
75	3.3	3.4	3.7
Mean	3.1	3.1	3.2

CD (P = 0.05)

Spacing : NS
Nitrogen : 0.34
S × N : 0.58